

Ocean Cryosphere Exchanges in Antarctica: Impacts on Climate and the Earth system

OCEAN:ICE data infrastructure 1

Milestone MS15

A screenshot of the SOOS map interface. The top left corner shows the "SOOS map" logo and an information icon. The main area displays a map of Antarctica. On the right side, there are navigation icons: a back arrow, a refresh icon, and a zoom control with plus and minus signs. Below the map, there are three tabs: "Datasets", "All Platforms", and "Credits". The "Credits" tab is active, showing a list of logos under the heading "Provided by". The logos include EMODnet, OCEAN:ICE, and SO-CHIC. Below this, under the heading "Data sources", there are logos for Argo, CCAMLR, IWEOT, SCAR, Copernicus Marine Service, glodap, EUMETSAT OSISAF, SeaDataNet, and ENA (European Nucleotide Archive).

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<https://ocean-ice.eu/>

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1 Means of verification of the achievement of the milestone:

This milestone concerns the design and deployment of the first version of the OCEAN:ICE data management infrastructure.

The verification of this milestone's achievements is facilitated through online access to the deployed services:

- Backend:
 - **ERDDAP**: <https://er1.s4oceanice.eu/erddap/index.html>
 - **GeoNetwork**: <https://catalog.s4oceanice.eu/geonetwork/>
- Frontend
 - **Portal**: <https://literacy.s4oceanice.eu/intro.html>

2 Work performed and main achievements

2.1 Backend Infrastructure

The current backend design of OCEAN:ICE is structured around two virtual machines (VMs, 2.10GHz processing power, 4 cores, 32GB RAM, running on CentOS with 500GB disk each). These VMs efficiently operate Docker containers, which, while resembling VMs, exhibit more relaxed isolation properties for sharing the underlying Operating System (OS) among applications.

In alignment with expectations, OCEAN:ICE has embraced Docker as its containerization solution, leveraging its comprehensive packages that include service tools, notably selected data publishing services. This choice underscores the project's commitment to a robust, flexible, and efficient backend infrastructure.

Fig. 1: Deployed architecture.

Access to the private area is managed through selective endpoint authorization, allowing access only from specified IP addresses or hosts with fully qualified domain names (FQDNs) and rejecting connections and access attempts from devices outside the authorized list.

Inspired by the Copernicus Marine Service Marine Data Store Dissemination Unit, the OCEAN:ICE Delivery Buffer introduces virtual folders for partners, providing a streamlined mechanism for depositing new data.

The OCEAN:ICE DMP recommends the adoption of an internal naming convention for new datasets, instrumental for the ingestion process, seamlessly transferring new data into the OCEAN:ICE database and data publication tools.

OCEAN:ICE employs ERDDAP as its designated data publishing tool, catering to both the OCEAN:ICE service layer (providing APIs and machine-to-machine services for internal use) and the OCEAN:ICE application layer (offering cataloguing features and machine-to-machine tools for external users).

ERDDAP is hosting data collections back-to-back with their metadata which (in compliance with FAIR principles) include common standards such as: ISO 8601 for the representation of date and time; SeaDataNet NVS P0x for the description of parameters; Climate and Forecasting conventions for standard names of parameters.; WGS84 for Datum; etc.

ERDDAP > List of All Datasets

9 matching datasets, listed in alphabetical order.

Grid DAP Data	Sub-set	Table DAP Data	Make A Graph	W M S	Source Data Files	Title	Summary	FGDC, ISO, Metadata	Back-ground Info	RSS	E mail	Institution	Dataset ID
	set	data	graph			* The List of All Active Datasets in this ERDDAP *		M	background			ETT S.p.A. - Peop...	allDatasets
		data	graph			Antarctic Tide Gauge Database		F I M	background			U.S. ANTARCTIC PR...	ANT_TG_OCEAN_HEIGHT
	set	data	graph			Australian Antarctic Program Survey Webcams		F I M	background			Australian Antarc...	Australian_Antarctic_Program
	set	data	graph			British Antarctica Survey Webcams		F I M	background			British Antartica...	British_Antarctica_Survey_webcams
	set	data	graph		files	Collection of OCEAN:ICE Argo Float Measurements - ARGO - In situ - MultiPointProfileObservation		F I M	background			OCEAN:ICE	ARGO_FLOATS_OCEANICE
		data	graph			Collection of XBT performed on the high density line IX28 (Dumont d Urville-Hobart) - 1990-2020		F I M	background			SOOP XBT	SURVOSTRAL
	data		graph	M		Ice Cover - 55-year Reanalysis 1957-present		F I M	background			RSMC, Japan Meteo...	RSMC_seaice
	data		graph	M		NOAA Optimum Interpolation (OI) SST V2 (sst.mmmean), 1.0°, 1981-present		F I M	background			National Centers ...	NOAA_OISST_v2
	data		graph		files	SOOS - Tracking of marine predators to protect Southern Ocean ecosystems		F I M	background			Australian Antarc...	SCAR_RAATD

The information in the table above is also available in other file formats (.csv, .htmlTable, .itx, .json, jsonCSV1, jsonCSV, jsonKVP, .mat, .nc, .ncsv, .tsv, .xhtml) via a RESTful web service.

ERDDAP, Version 2.23
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Fig.2: OCEAN:ICE ERDDAP datasets.

These metadata components are considered fundamental for adopting a FAIRE (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable, Extensible) data approach and are consistently applied to all datasets generated by the project.

The minimum metadata are: platform id, platform type, sensor model, contributors' role, naming authority, Institution, QC method, group parameters, variable names, unit, Quality Flag Scheme, time, datum, country, licence, INSPIRE, PI, data doi, project, funding.

Fig. 4: SOOSmap data portal

Fig. 5: OCEAN:ICE ARGO.

Fig. 6: Platform page.